

Settlement of Land Disputes in Bangladesh: Legal Issues and Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Settlement of land disputes that causes never-ending dilemma in the life of a considerable portion of the population is one of the major challenges Bangladesh is now encountering. It mounts a huge case backlog on the already over-burden judiciary. Due to flawed legal framework, procrastination in judicial land dispute settlement and widespread corruption in land administration, settlement of land disputes in Bangladesh is very complicated, tiresome as well as lengthy and expensive. This article summarizes the various kinds of land related disputes in Bangladesh with a view to identifying the legal issues and challenges in settlement of such disputes. As a part of the analytical approach, the paper makes a critical analysis of the existing legal scholarships, relevant legislations and case laws. The author argues that the old-fashioned land management system requires major reforms with a view to addressing the legal issues in settlement of land disputes in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Land disputes, Mutation, Record of Rights, Pre-emption, Automation of Land Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Bangladesh, land disputes usually arise out of conflicts or disputes over the possession and title of the same land or discords regarding the boundary of land between and among two or more claimants.¹ The land distribution system may be treated as one of the reasons of land disputes creating inequality and grievance amongst the people and causing a barrier to establish economic and social justice. Here some people are having hundreds of *bighas* of land and some have not got any.² Such an unequal distribution of land, scarcity of land due to over population and particularly illegal occupation of land by unscrupulous people showing muscle power and money leads to land disputes. Such disputes over land give birth to most of the conflicts and violence in rural or urban areas since more than 80% litigations either civil or criminal arise out of land related disputes.³ One in every seven households in Bangladesh is involved in land disputes.⁴ This paper will make an inquest into the various forms of land disputes in Bangladesh and enquire into the underlying

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¹ Miah, Abdul Kader, *Bhumi Jarip o Bhumi Babasthapana*, A. K. Prokashani, Dhaka, 2011, p. 333.

² Islam, Mohammad Towhidul, *The Development of Land Laws and Land Administration in Bangladesh*, *The Dhaka University Studies Part - F*, Vol. 16, No. 2, December 2005, p. 204.

³ *Ibid*, p. 205.

⁴ Rahman, Ashiqur, *'Socio-Economic Costs of Property Disputes: An Empirical Examination from Bangladesh'*, Policy Research Institute, BRAC, Dhaka, 2015.

causes of those disputes so as to make a contribution to simplify the procedure of land dispute settlement in Bangladesh.

2. CONCEPTUALIZING THE LAND DISPUTES

Generally, what we mean by the term 'land' is that the surface of the earth used as human habitation, cultivation and for the purpose of manufacturing and industry. Though the literal meaning of land is immovable, the term extends also to the meaning of rights in and over the immovable.⁵ Osborn's Concise Law Dictionary defines 'land' as any ground, soil or earth whatsoever.⁶ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act hereinafter called as SAT Act defined the word 'land' as 'land which is cultivated or uncultivated, or covered with water, at any time of the year and includes benefits to arise of land, houses of buildings and also things attached to the earth or permanently fastened to anything attached to the earth.'⁷The immovable property includes land which is cultivated, uncultivated or covered with water at the time of the year.⁸ It also includes things attached to the earth comprising houses or buildings or standing trees but not standing timber, growing-crops or grass since they will be cut sooner or later.⁹

The term 'dispute' has not been defined in the statute but what is meant by a dispute is a disagreement between two people or to question whether something is true and valid. A land dispute may occur when two people feel that they both have a legal claim to a piece of land. For instance, co-sharers in a family may have dispute regarding ancestral land while the neighboring owners may have conflict over land boundaries. In Bangladesh, land disputes mainly arise out of purchasing disputed lands as well as the land owners' ignorance of the land related laws and rules. The age-old legal system and corruption at almost all tiers of land administration are also responsible for land disputes.¹⁰ Land disputes in most of the cases are related with modes of obtaining land ownership. A person may have a dispute while obtaining land ownership in various ways namely inheritance,¹¹ purchase,¹² *aluvion*¹³ and *diluvion*, acquisition and requisition of land,¹⁴ *heba* (Gift)¹⁵ will, *waqf* (endowment)¹⁶ and trust¹⁷ auction purchase,¹⁸ by decree of courts and so forth.

⁵ Islam, Mohammad Towhidul, *Land Law, Texts, Cases and Materials*, Dhaka, Centre for Human Rights and Legal Research, Bangladesh, 2018, P. 19.

⁶ Roger Bird (eds.), Osborn's Concise Law Dictionary, 7th ed. Universal Law Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd, Delhi, 1983, 195.

⁷ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 2(16).

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ *Bajjnath v. Ramadhar and Anr*, AIR 1963, All, 214.

¹⁰ Saleh, Mohammad Faysal, 'Drawbacks of land administration system in Bangladesh and some feasible solutions', BDBLD, Dhaka, 2015 < bdlawdigest.org/drawbacks-of-land-administration-system-in-bangladesh-and-some-feasible-solutions.html > (retrieved on 25 February 2018).

¹¹ According to personal laws, e.g. Muslim Law, Hindu Law, etc.

¹² See, the Transfer of Property Act (Act No. IV of 1882), S. 54, the State Acquisition and Tenancy Act (Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 89.

¹³ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act (Act No. XXVIII of 1951), Ss. 86 and 87.

¹⁴ The Acquisition and Requisition of Immoveable Property Act, 2017 (Act No. 21 of 2017).

¹⁵ Personal laws read with section 17 of the Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908).

¹⁶ The Waqfs Ordinance, 1962 (East Pakistan Ordinance No. I of 1962).

¹⁷ The Trusts Act, 1882 (Act No. II of 1882).

¹⁸ The Public Demands Recovery Act, 1913 (Bengal Act No. III of 1913).

2. DIFFERENT TYPES OF LAND DISPUTES

The land administration and land management system in Bangladesh is very weak and vulnerable. Since the land administration and land management are not fully digitized,¹⁹ the land records along with other public record keeping in Bangladesh are so old age and susceptible to corruption. Such a fragile management and old fashioned land system gives rise to various disputes among the land owners and users. In this outset, an attempt has been made to pinpoint the grounds of various land disputes as well as to explicate the nature of such disputes.

3.1. Dispute relating to Sale of Land

Sale, among all other means, is the most common means of transfer of landed property. As such most of the disputes relating to landed property arise out of sale. Disputes as to sale of land arises when a landed property is sold out without title or by a legally disabled person, false personation, fraud and so forth.

Sale without title or by false personation

If any person sells a piece of land without having title over it, the transfer is not valid and legal. Sometimes, disputes arise in case a person sells the land belonging to another by means of false personation.²⁰ In such circumstances, the aggrieved person may take civil and criminal actions.²¹ The provisions of criminal actions are laid down in sections 420 and 465 of the Penal Code.²² The transferee may lodge a First Information Report (FIR) with the concerned Police Station with the allegation of cheating and forgery. As per the provisions of the Specific Relief Act, the aggrieved persons may sue to the competent civil court to have the said deed of sale cancelled and to have compensations.²³

Sale by legally disabled person

A legally disabled person such as minor,²⁴ insane²⁵ or lunatic²⁶ is not entitled to dispose of his/her property.²⁷ A person is said to be minor until he attains the age of 18 or 21 if the person and property of the minor are under the Court of Ward or a legal guardian as appointed by the court.²⁸ However, sometimes the legally disabled persons are found to have sold their land violating the provision of law. These sales are not valid and as such, the deeds of that sale may be challenged in the court under section 39 of the Specific Relief Act.

¹⁹ Md. Shafiqul Islam, How far has land management been digitized? *The Dhaka Tribune*, March 25, 2018, available at <https://www.dhakatribune.com/bangladesh/2018/03/24/much-effective-digital-land-management>, accessed on August 10, 2019.

²⁰ Also referred to as assuming the identity of another person with intent to deceive. *Vide*, section 205 of the Penal Code, 1860 (Act No. XLV of 1860).

²¹ *Vide*, Sections 420, 465 of the Penal Code, 1860 (Act No. XLV of 1860); sections 39, 41 of the Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877).

²² The Penal Code, 1860 (Act No. XLV of 1860).

²³ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877), Ss. 39, 41.

²⁴ The Contract Act, 1872 (Act No. IX of 1872), Ss. 11, 12.

²⁵ *Ibid*.

²⁶ *Ibid*.

²⁷ The Limitation Act, 1908 (Act No. IX of 1908), S. 6.

²⁸ The Majority Act, 1875 (Act No IX of 1875), S. 3.

Sale in mutual mistakes

Owing to mutual mistakes of the seller and the buyer or clerical errors as caused by the deed writer, plot numbers, *khatiyan*²⁹ numbers or *mouza*³⁰ of the land may often be mistakenly written in the sale deeds. In such a situation the party aggrieved may institute a suit to have the deed rectified.³¹

Sale by fraud, coercion, undue influence or misrepresentation

If a deed of sale is solemnized by means of fraud,³² coercion,³³ undue influence³⁴ or misrepresentation,³⁵ the same is voidable at the option of the aggrieved person. Suits may be instituted to the competent courts to have the deeds either rectified under section 31 of the Specific Relief Act, 1877 or cancelled under section 39 of the same Act.

Dispute relating to contract for sale of land

A contract for sale also known as *bainanama* shall be in writing, executed by the parties, and registered³⁶ and presented for registration within thirty days from the date of execution of the contract.³⁷ A time to be reckoned from the date of registration shall be mentioned for execution and registration of the instrument of sale, and if no time is mentioned, the time shall be deemed to be six months.³⁸ Disputes usually arise when the seller refuses to receive the rest of the consideration money and execute and register the deed of sale for the buyer. Under this circumstance, the buyer may institute a suit for specific performance of contract.³⁹

3.2. Dispute relating to Pre-emption Right

The right of pre-emption entitles a right holder to get preferentially a land sold to a third party by paying a price equal to that other settled or paid by the latter.⁴⁰ In Bangladesh, apart from the Muslim Law, there are two main statutes, namely, the State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (SAT Act)⁴¹ and the Non-Agricultural Tenancy Act, 1949 (NAT Act)⁴² containing the right of pre-emption for agricultural and non-agricultural land respectively. In a claim for pre-emption with regard to agricultural land, a pre-emption (miscellaneous) case is to be recorded under section 96 of the SAT Act and for non-agricultural land, a pre-emption (miscellaneous) case is usually filed under section 24 of the NAT Act. In the case of pre-emption under statutory laws (SAT and NAT Acts), the proceeding is called miscellaneous case and it starts with an application and under Muslim law, the proceeding is called a pre-emption suit which starts with a plaint. In a pre-emption

²⁹ *Khatiyan* means record of rights (ROR).

³⁰ *Mouza* which is synonymous with 'gram/village' refers to the lowest revenue collection unit.

³¹ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877), S. 31.

³² The Contract Act, 1872 (Act No. IX of 1872), S. 16.

³³ *Ibid*, S. 17.

³⁴ *Ibid*, S.18.

³⁵ *Ibid*, S.19.

³⁶ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908), S. 17A.

³⁷ *Ibid*, S. 17A (2).

³⁸ The Transfer of Property Act, 1882 (Act No. IV of 1882), S. 54A.

³⁹ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877), S. 12.

⁴⁰ Md. Towhidul Islam & Shirin Sultana, Nature of Land and Pre-emption suits: Demystifying Ambiguities, *Dhaka University Law Journal*, 2018, available at <https://univdhaka.academia.edu/MohammadTowhidulIslam>, accessed on 10 October 2019.

⁴¹ East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951.

⁴² East Bengal Act No. XXIII of 1949.

case or suit, the court has to settle a number of issues including who are entitled to apply for pre-emption, what is the nature of land and so forth.

3.3. Dispute relating to Partition of Land

Partition of an undivided or *ejmali* property refers to the division of the same among the co-sharers in proportionate to their respective *saham* or shares. As such, partition is a process by which members of an undivided family get separate.⁴³ However, partition is not a transfer of property. According to the respective personal law, the landed property gets divided and partitioned following any of the three modes namely amicable partition, *salish* or filing a partition suit. Then the co-sharers are to execute a deed of partition and get the same registered. Finally, the co-sharers have to get the respective shares mutated⁴⁴ in their names.

Dispute relating to partition of landed property arises when a co-sharer takes larger share than the actual share he will have or vice versa and the property remains undivided at the disposal of one or more sharers. In our country, in most of the cases the heirs own and possess the inherited properties in *ejmali* through an amicable settlement. Therefore, in the absence of a written partition deed between or among the co-sharers, dispute arises between or among them with regard to the allotment of the respective shares or sometimes as to possession of the particular plot. Such disputes ultimately find their way to courts.⁴⁵

3.4. Dispute relating to Possession of Land

Generally dispute relating to possession arises out of encroachment or grabbing of land, threats of dispossession and forceful dispossession. If a person crosses the boundary of his land and erects any structure on the land of others or builds a house projecting the sunset over the land of others or violating the rules of municipal or City Corporation, the aggrieved party may sue against the encroacher to have the part projecting over the land of neighbor pulled down.⁴⁶ An order of temporary injunction⁴⁷ may also be sought from the court restraining the person from erecting the structure beyond the permitted level.

In case a person invades or threatens to invade the possession or enjoyment of landed property of any person, the person whose possession has been threatened may move to the court with a petition for the perpetual injunction⁴⁸ along with an order for temporary injunction.⁴⁹ The aggrieved person whose property is under threats may also file a petition to the Executive Magistrate under sections 144 or 145 of the CrPC.⁵⁰ In case a person has been dispossessed forcefully without due process of law, he may file a suit to have the possession recovered.⁵¹

3.5. Dispute relating to Mortgage

The nature of the dispute under mortgage is usually redemption and foreclosure. If the mortgagee refuses to restore the possession of the mortgaged property to the mortgagor any time after the

⁴³ Partition Act, 1893 (Act No. 4 of 1893) S. 4.

⁴⁴ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), Sections 117 and 143B.

⁴⁵ The Partition Act (Act No. 4 of 1893) Ss. 2, 4.

⁴⁶ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877) S. 55.

⁴⁷ The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908, Order 39, Rule 1.

⁴⁸ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877) S. 54.

⁴⁹ The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908, Order 39, Rule 1.

⁵⁰ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, Ss. 144, 145.

⁵¹ The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877), Ss. 8, 9.

mortgage money has been paid, the mortgagor is entitled to redeem the property⁵² file a suit against the mortgagee for restoration of possession of the mortgaged property. In case of a complete usufructuary mortgage,⁵³ the mortgagor may file a suit to a competent civil court or a petition to Assistant Commissioner (Land) for restoration or redemption of the land.⁵⁴In the case of *Abu Baker vs. Nazir Ahmed*,⁵⁵it was held that section 95 gives the mortgagor the right to get back his property by application to a Magistrate. In the case of *Jahir Ahmed vs. Badsha Mia Sowdagor*,⁵⁶ it was held that sub-section (4) of section 95 of the Act does not debar filing a civil suit by the mortgagor.

3.6. Dispute relating to Record of Rights (ROR)

Record of rights, also known in Bangla ‘*khatiyani*’ refers to a document that contains the description of land along with the particulars of the title or rights of the land owner. Though the record of rights is the best evidence of the present possession in favour of the owner, the same is not a document of title. In the case *Hameed Ali vs. Rahela Khatun*,⁵⁷it was held that the survey officials have not been given any authority under the Act to declare while preparing the record of rights⁵⁸ the title of any person. Dispute relating to record of rights arises out of exclusion of the name of the owner, inclusion of the name of the illegal possessor, mistakes in mentioning the area of land in the plot number or leaving out of a plot number in the *mouza* map.

In case the land owner comes to know about the aforesaid disputes during preparation of the record of rights, he may institute a miscellaneous proceeding at the office of Settlement Officer under the Tenancy Rules⁵⁹ which is generally called as 30 *dharar apotti mamla*. If he fails to have the records of rights corrected, he may prefer an appeal to the Settlement Officer under rule 31 against the decision of the Settlement Officer.⁶⁰If a dispute as to the correctness of record of rights appears after the final publication of record of rights, the aggrieved person may file suit for correction of record of rights to Land Survey Tribunal. An appeal can be preferred against the decision of the Land Survey Tribunal to the Land Survey Appellate Tribunal. In case the Land Survey Tribunal is not set up in a district, the aggrieved person may institute a declaratory suit to a competent civil court to have his title declared which has been clouded through an illegal preparation of record of rights.⁶¹

3.7. Dispute relating to Mutation

The legal process of updating the land record through adding of names of the new owners and excluding the names of the old owners in the event of change of ownerships in land is called mutation. Usually a dispute as to mutation arises when the name of a person is mutated against a piece of land having no title over it. Upon receiving a mutation application or a land transfer notice, the Assistant Commissioner (Land) after opening a mutation case,⁶² send the file to the *Tehshildar*

⁵² The Transfer of Property Act (Act No. IV of 1882), S. 60.

⁵³ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 2(6).

⁵⁴ *Ibid*, S. 95.

⁵⁵ 34 DLR (AD) 237.

⁵⁶ 36 DLR 90.

⁵⁷ 14 DLR 603.

⁵⁸ The impression within bracket is added by the author.

⁵⁹ The Tenancy Rules, 1955, Rules 30.

⁶⁰ *Ibid*, Rules 31.

⁶¹ The Specific Relief Act, 1877, (Act No. I of 1877), S. 42.

⁶² The Assistant Commissioner (Land) opens a miscellaneous case in Register 9.

for necessary verification and report. A notice in this regard shall have to be issued to all other co-sharers.⁶³ In the case *Tofajjol Hossain vs. Momotaj Begum*,⁶⁴ it was held that if a mutation is done without service notice to other co-sharers, the same will have no legal effect. Then on receipt of the proposal for mutation⁶⁵ from the *Tahshilder* and hearing both parties, the Assistant Commissioner (Land) shall allow the mutation application with an order for sub-division of the joint holding among the co-sharers.

Dispute does usually arise in case the mutation is done without service of the notice to other co-sharers. In this case the aggrieved party may apply to Assistant Commissioner (Land) concerned within 30 days from the date of the order for mutation under section 150 of the SAT Act⁶⁶ to have the said mutation order reviewed. The Assistant Commissioner (Land) may modify, reverse, or confirm the mutation order passed earlier.

3.8. Dispute relating to Acquisition and Requisition of Land

Acquisition and requisition mean to take over the private property by the government for public interest and public purpose. The government has the lawful authority to acquire any land except mosques, graveyards and other religious structures.⁶⁷ Dispute of this kind arises in case of under assessment of the property value, non-consideration of damages caused for acquisition or requisition of property, exclusion of any heirs of the property to be acquired or requisitioned from compensation, entitlement to receive compensation and apportionment of compensation.

Disputes mentioned above may be settled by presenting a petition of objection to the Deputy Commissioner (DC).⁶⁸ The DC is to prepare the award of compensation to be paid to the parties whose properties are intended to be acquisitioned and requisitioned.⁶⁹ If any party to the award of compensation made by the DC is dissatisfied, he may apply to the Arbitrator within 45 days of the decision.⁷⁰ The decision of Arbitrator as to the award shall be deemed to a decree and judgment⁷¹ which is appealable to the Arbitration Appellate Tribunal.⁷² The decision of the Appellate Tribunal shall be final.⁷³

3.9. Dispute relating to *Khas* Land

Khas land means government owned fallow land, where nobody has property rights. It is land which is deemed to be owned by the government and available for allocation according to government priorities.⁷⁴ *Khas* land absolutely vests in the Government and remains in the '*Khas*

⁶³ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950, S. 117(1) c.

⁶⁴ 52 DLR (2000) 223.

⁶⁵ After necessary verification, the *Tahshilder* usually submits proposal which is known as *namjari o joma bhager prostab patro*.

⁶⁶ State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951).

⁶⁷ The Acquisition and Requisition of Immovable Property Act, 2017 (Act No. 21 of 2017) S. 4(13).

⁶⁸ *Ibid*, Ss. 5, 21.

⁶⁹ *Ibid*, Ss. 8, 22.

⁷⁰ *Ibid*, S. 30.

⁷¹ *Ibid*, S. 34(3).

⁷² *Ibid*, S. 36(1).

⁷³ *Ibid*, S. 36(4).

⁷⁴ Judicial Dictionary, Chancery Law Chronicles, available at <https://www.clcbd.org/lawdictionary/159.html>, retrieved on 16 October 2019.

possession' of the Government.⁷⁵ The land of this kind is recorded in the *Khatiyon* No.1 in the name of the Collector in the Register No. 8.⁷⁶ The Government is empowered to make settlement of *khas* land in accordance with the rules as it may make in this behalf or to use or otherwise deal with such land in such manner as it thinks fit.⁷⁷ The settlement must be created through a registered deed as section 81B of SAT Act⁷⁸ provides that no agricultural or non-agricultural tenancy shall in law be created until a deed of lease has been executed in favour of the lessee by a competent authority and the said lease has been duly registered.⁷⁹

The nature of the disputes with regard to *khas* land include, *inter alia*, settlement of the same *khas* land to different persons, settlement of *khas* land to a person who is not landless or to persons who did not get possession of the land settled in their favour. In the event of any dispute of this kind, the aggrieved party has mostly to resort to the administrative remedy rather than to move to the court. Section 76(2) has ousted the Civil Court's jurisdiction to entertain any application or suit concerning any matter relating to the settlement of any *khas* land.⁸⁰ It was held by the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court that the Government is the highest authority to pass any order as to the settlement and the civil court cannot interfere with the same unless the same is *mala fide* and *coram non-judice*.⁸¹ A person aggrieved with the decision made by the Deputy Commissioner (DC) with regard to settlement of *khas* land may move a petition to the DC to review his decision and against the order on the petition may prefer an appeal to higher authority. In case the aggrieved person gets no remedy, he may prefer a petition to the civil court to have a mandatory injunction.⁸² It was held in *Abdul Majid vs. Province of East Pakistan*⁸³ that a suit filed by the plaintiff challenging order of cancellation of their settlement by the Commissioner was not barred.

3.10. Dispute relating to Probate and Letters of Administration

Probates and letters of administration are the grant of authority by the courts to deal with the estate of a deceased. Disputes regarding probate and letters of administration arise when the heirs of the deceased repudiate to consent to a 'will' as declared by the testator, or the heirs claim of forgery about the deed of a 'will' or bequest.

Probate means the copy of a 'will' certified under the seal of a court of competent jurisdiction with a grant of administration to the estate of the testator.⁸⁴ While making a 'will' the testator usually appoints an executor to legally deal with his assets after his death. Accordingly, the executor can cash in the assets and transfer to the beneficiaries of the 'will'. However, the executor is required to have a probate from the competent courts. Through issuing of probate, the court confirms that the 'will' is valid and the executor is authorized to deal with the estate.⁸⁵

⁷⁵ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 76.

⁷⁶ The Government State Manual 1958.

⁷⁷ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), Ss. 76, 77A, 78; the State Acquisition Rules, 1951, Rule 83; the Agricultural *Khas* Land Management and Settlement Policy, 1997 & Non-Agricultural *Khas* Land Management and Settlement Policy, 1995.

⁷⁸ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 81B.

⁷⁹ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908), S. 17(1) (d).

⁸⁰ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 76 (2).

⁸¹ 24 BCR (AD) 25.

⁸² The Specific Relief Act, 1877 (Act No. I of 1877), S. 55.

⁸³ 30 DLR 232.

⁸⁴ The Succession Act, 1925 (Act No. XXXIX of 1925), S. 2(f).

⁸⁵ *Ibid*, S. 227.

Letters of administration are issued usually to the legal heirs⁸⁶ in one of the two circumstances. Firstly, where a person dies without making a ‘will’ and secondly where there is a valid ‘will’ but the executor is not willing or no more capable of dealing with the estate. Letters of administration entitles the administrator to all rights belonging to the intestate as effectually as if the administration had been granted at the moment after his death.⁸⁷

3.11. Dispute relating to Enemy and Vested Property

The vested property was known in Pakistan as enemy property during the period of 1965-1971.⁸⁸ According to the Defence of Pakistan Ordinance⁸⁹ and Rules,⁹⁰ all assets and interests of Indian citizens within Pakistan were declared as the enemy properties which were taken over by the Deputy Commissioner (DC) as the custodian for management and control. After the independence of Bangladesh, the status of enemy property was changed into vested property.⁹¹ Subsequently, the Vested Property Return Act⁹² was promulgated with a view to returning the vested property to the *bona fide* owners or their heirs.⁹³ All vested properties were enlisted in list ‘Ka’ and ‘Kha’.⁹⁴

Disputes regarding vested properties arise out of illegal and improper enlisting of landed property as the vested properties. The owner of the land enlisted as vested property in list ‘ka’, may, within 300 days of the gazette notification, file a petition to the Tribunal⁹⁵ for release of the land from the list.⁹⁶ The person aggrieved with the decision of the Tribunal may, within 45 days, prefer an appeal to the Appellate Tribunal.⁹⁷

3.12. Dispute relating to Easement Right

Easement means a right possessed by the owner of a land for beneficial enjoyment of his own land to do or continue to do something or prevent something from being done in other land not his own.⁹⁸ Disputes arise out of impending or disturbance of such easement rights. The owner or occupier of the dominant heritage⁹⁹ is entitled to enjoy the easement without disturbance by any other person.¹⁰⁰ In case of any obstruction or disturbance to enjoyment of easement right, a suit for compensation may be instituted, provided that the disturbance has actually caused substantial

⁸⁶ Ibid, S. 218.

⁸⁷ Ibid, S. 220.

⁸⁸ Banglapedia, National Encyclopedia of Bangladesh, *Vested Property*, available at http://en.banglapedia.org/index.php?title=Vested_Property, retrieved on 19 October 2019.

⁸⁹ The Defence of Pakistan Ordinance, 1965.

⁹⁰ The Defence of Pakistan Rules, 1965.

⁹¹ The Enemy Property (Continuance of Emergency Provisions) (Repeal) Act, 1974 (XLV of 1974).

⁹² The Vested Property Return Act, 2001 (Act No. 16 of 2001).

⁹³ The Vested Property Return, 2001 (Act No. 16 of 2001) S. 5.

⁹⁴ List *Kha* was set aside by section 24 of the Vested Property Return (Second Amendment) Act, 2013 (Act No. 46 of 2013).

⁹⁵ The Vested Property Return Act, 2001 (Act No. 16 of 2001) S. 16. (The government may, through gazette notification, establish one or more Tribunals in each District.)

⁹⁶ The Vested Property Return Act, 2001 (Act No. 16 of 2001) S. 10(1).

⁹⁷ Ibid, S. 18.

⁹⁸ The Easement Act, 1882 (Act No. V of 1882), S. 4.

⁹⁹ The land for the beneficial enjoyment of which the right exists is called the dominant heritage, and the owner or occupier thereof the dominant owner; the land on which the liability is imposed is called the servient heritage, and the owner or occupier thereof the servient owner.

¹⁰⁰ The Easement Act, 1882 (Act No. V of 1882), S. 32.

damage to the plaintiff.¹⁰¹ Apart from compensation, an injunction may also be sought to restrain the disturbance of the easement.¹⁰²

4. LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR SETTLEMENT OF LAND DISPUTES

In Bangladesh, the legal framework providing for both formal and informal mechanisms with regard to the settlement of land disputes exists. People resort to any of these to get their disputes settled. Each mechanism has its own procedure of settling disputes. Both the mechanisms have their own strengths and weakness in resolving land disputes. The formal mechanisms include civil courts, land survey tribunals as well as the high court divisions and the appellate divisions of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh.

Civil Courts

According to existing law, all suits of civil nature are exclusively within the jurisdiction of the civil courts.¹⁰³ Suits of civil nature mean suits which involve right to a property or to an office.¹⁰⁴ Right to property includes all kinds of property either moveable or immovable. Practically, the immovable property refers to landed property and as such almost all the land disputes in Bangladesh find their ways in civil courts for settlement.

However, settlement of land disputes through civil courts is time consuming, costly and complex. The reasons include, *inter alia*, back logs of cases, flaws in existing laws, scarcity of efficient judicial staff and widespread corruption. A statistics shows that about 2.5 million operating land litigation including 1.4 million pending suits are clogging the courts annually affecting 120 million people by land litigation.¹⁰⁵ According to a hypothesis drawn in the statistics, the estimated time to dispose of such ever increasing suits is equivalent to 27 million years, the cumulative amount of money spent to meet litigation cost is higher than the annual development budget of the country and the annual amount of incidental expenses is Tk. 248, 599 million with 50 percent as bribe.¹⁰⁶ Another study reveals that adjudication of the pending suits relating to land disputes will cost about 45% of annual household income.¹⁰⁷

The Land Survey Tribunals

The Government established Land Survey Tribunals and Land Survey Appellate Tribunals in 2004 with view to settling disputes arising out of final publication of the last revised record of rights prepared under section 144.¹⁰⁸ Suits of this kind instituted in any civil court before the establishment of the Land Survey Tribunal were transferred to the Tribunal as soon as the same was established. With a view to hearing and disposal of appeals arising out the judgment, decree or order of the Land Survey Tribunals, the government is supposed to establish the Land Survey

¹⁰¹ Ibid, S. 33.

¹⁰² Ibid, S. 35 read with sections 52-57 of the Specific Relief Act of 1877 (Act No. I of 1877).

¹⁰³ The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908, (Act No. V of 1908), S. 9.

¹⁰⁴ Mohammad Hamidul Haque, *Trial of Civil Suits and Criminal Cases*, Universal Book House, Dhaka, 2010, P. 3.

¹⁰⁵ Barkat, Abul and Prashanto K. Roy, *Political Economy of Land Litigation in Bangladesh: A Case of Colossal National Wastage*, Dhaka, ALRD, 2004.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ Rahman, Ashiqur, 'Socio-Economic Costs of Property Disputes: An Empirical Examination from Bangladesh', Policy Research Institute, BRAC, Dhaka, 2015.

¹⁰⁸ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S. 145A. For this purpose, a new Chapter XVIIIA was inserted by section 2 of the State Acquisition and Tenancy (Amendment) Act, 2004 (Act No. IX of 2004).

Appellate Tribunal headed by a High Court Judge.¹⁰⁹ However, no such Appellate Tribunal was formed in the last 15 years after formation of law to this effect.¹¹⁰ Aggrieved parties have to file writ petition with the High Court Division (HCD) challenging the tribunals' decision in absence of land survey appellate tribunals. The HCD takes long time to settle land related writ petitions since it is burdened with other cases. Moreover, the Land Survey Tribunals are hard hit by backlog of cases causing public suffering due to lack of judges and other logistics, causing immense sufferings to the people. The number of cases pending before 44 land tribunals across the country has hiked to 3 lakh now.¹¹¹ Provided the current scenario of case disposal, it would take around 33 years to dispose of the existing cases in Dhaka alone. The government has decided to amend the law to expedite the settlement of land disputes arising out records of rights.¹¹² Accordingly, the existing land tribunals will be abolished and the Assistant Judges and other judicial officials will get power to settle land record disputes.

The Village Courts

The village court has its origin in the traditional *shalish* system and as such most of its functional aspect is based on the *shalish* system.¹¹³ It has both civil and criminal jurisdictions.¹¹⁴ Disputes relating to recovery of a landed property or the price thereof, recovery of the possession of land and recovery of compensation for the illegal possession of land may be disposed off when the value of the land does not exceed Tk. 75000.¹¹⁵ Compared to procedure in the ordinary courts, the adjudication process in the village court is largely informal.¹¹⁶ However, the pecuniary jurisdiction of the village court narrowed down the scope of settling the land disputes through this forum.

Digital Land Management System (DLMS)

Different ministries and departments are involved in land administration of Bangladesh. The Ministry of Land looks after the survey and record issues, while the Ministry of Law handles the registration process. Most of the officials discharging land related functions under the Ministry of Land are on deputation from the Ministry of Public Administration. Therefore, the one needs to visit more than ten government offices for collecting documents. These offices are crammed with handwritten paper documents and registers of almost hundred years old. Many of those are already damaged either due to humidity or half-eaten by booklice, wood worms, termites, mice and cockroaches. The absence of an updated database is the major reason behind land disputes. A central database is needed for having a comprehensive link to all land-related organizations under a single network.¹¹⁷

¹⁰⁹ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (East Bengal Act No. XXVIII of 1951), S.

¹¹⁰ On November 12, 2019, in response to a writ petition challenging a judgment delivered by Land Survey Tribunal in Chandpur, the HCD ordered the government to inform the reasons, behind not formation of the Land Survey Appellate Tribunal in the last 15 years.

¹¹¹ *The Daily Sun*, December 3, 2019.

¹¹² The notification issued by the Ministry Law, Justice and Parliamentary Affairs on June 25, 2018.

¹¹³ Stephen Golub, Non-State Justice Systems in Bangladesh and Philippines, 2003 (prepared for the DFID, UK).

¹¹⁴ The Village Court Act, 2006 (Act No. 19 of 2006) S. 3.

¹¹⁵ *Ibid*, Second Schedule, Articles 2, 3 and 4.

¹¹⁶ *Ibid*, Ss. 13 and 14.

¹¹⁷ The Financial Express, 5 July 2018, <https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/why-is-automation-of-land-registration-taking-so-much-time-1530721504>.

The government has undertaken a pilot project titled, 'Land Management Automation' with a view to bringing the country's land management within a computerized system.¹¹⁸ It will certainly strengthen access to Land and property rights to all citizens of Bangladesh. However, the project is yet to see the light of the day. The lack of dedication and earnestness of the public service providers along with the fear of losing extra earnings and jobs by a section of people, involved with the century-old land management, is attributed to be the reason behind the delay.

5. LEGAL ISSUES

The issues usually involve in settlement of land disputes are very complicated, unlimited and tiresome. An owner should have both title and possession either actual or constructive over the land he claimed to own otherwise his ownership would be questionable. Whether the ownership (title) of a person in respect of a piece of land is genuine or not is a very complex issue. Different modes and documents are to be considered in order to establish the ownership.

5.1. Deed of Title

Depending on the mode of acquiring ownership over a piece of land, deed of title is of various types namely deed of sale (*saf kabala* deed), exchange deed, deed of *heba* or gift, deed of will, partition deed or succession certificate. The sale is a transfer of ownership in exchange for a price paid or promised or part-paid and part-promised.¹¹⁹ However, a sale of immovable property can be made only by registered instrument.¹²⁰ A registered deed of sale can be verified or inspected and certified copy of the same can be taken on depositing prescribed fees from the office in which the deed was registered.¹²¹

A person can have title on land by means of exchange. Exchange refers to the mutual transfer of respective ownerships of two individuals in two different specific properties for which the parties are to execute two separate deeds. It is different from sale inasmuch as sale is always for a price which means money. In case of exchange, it is not the price to be paid; rather one specific property is transferred for another.¹²² Like a deed of sale, the deeds of exchange must be registered.¹²³

An individual may acquire land by means of gift as defined in the Transfer of Property Act¹²⁴ or *heba* as provided by the Muslim law. For the purpose of solemnizing a gift of immovable property, the transfer must be affected by a registered instrument signed by or on behalf of the donor and attested by at least two witnesses. According to section 17(1)(a) of the Registration Act, 1908, the registration of instrument of gift of immovable property is compulsory. The provision of gifts under the Transfer of Property Act applies to any person making gift in Bangladesh irrespective of religion and castes. However, the same does not affect the right of a Muslim to make *heba* under Muslim law.¹²⁵

¹¹⁸ Land management automation project, the Independent, 18 September 2017, <http://www.theindependentbd.com/arcprint/details/114525/2017-09-18>.

¹¹⁹ The Transfer of Property Act, 1882 (Act No. IV of 1882) S. 54.

¹²⁰ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908) S. 17(1) (b).

¹²¹ Arif Jamil, Verification of Documents of Land, *the Dhaka University Studies Part-F*, Vol. 17, No. 1, 2006, P. 188.

¹²² Ibid, P. 189.

¹²³ The Transfer of Property Act, 1882 (Act No. IV of 1882) S. 118.

¹²⁴ Ibid, S. 122.

¹²⁵ Ibid, S.

Declaration of *heba* falls within the ambit of personal law of the Muslim in which the rule of decision is the Muslim personal law.¹²⁶ The essentials of *heba* under Muslim law are declaration of *heba* by the donor, acceptance by the donee and delivery of possession of the property to the donee. A *heba* under Muslim law did not require a written deed and registration since 2005. Now a declaration of *heba* of immovable property under Muslim personal law '*sharia*' must be effected through a registered deed.¹²⁷

A person may acquire a piece of land by means of 'will or *wasiyat*' that takes effect following the death of the testator. As the registration of an instrument of 'will' is not mandatory by the Registration Act, one can own a piece of land by virtue of a deed of 'will' which may or may not be registered.¹²⁸ However, the testator, or after his death any person claiming as executor or otherwise under a will, may present it to any Registrar or Sub-Registrar for registration.¹²⁹ Document of 'will' presented for registration may be registered in the same manner as any other document.¹³⁰ The registering officer is to be satisfied that the will was executed by the testator, that the testator is dead and that the person presenting the will is, under section 40, entitled to present the same.¹³¹

In the event of a piece of land acquired by means of inheritance, the successor has to have a succession certificate or a registered partition deed. As it is provided by the Registration Act, an instrument of partition of immovable property affected by persons upon inheritance according to their respective personal laws must be registered.¹³²

5.2. *Bia* deed

A *bia* deed refers to the deed of previous owner which is produced to show whom the land is bought from. It supports title of the present owner. *Bia* deeds are very essential to establish the chain of ownership in land. For the purpose of registration, it is required to furnish in the registration form a brief description of the ownership of the property for the last 25 (twenty-five) years.¹³³ During that period a land can be transferred more than once¹³⁴ and as such there may be several *bia* deeds that indicate who were the previous owners of that land.

5.3. Record of Rights/ *Khatian*

Record of Rights or *khatian* is of various types namely CS *khatian*, SA *khatian*, RS *khatian*, BS *khatian*, Dhaka City *gorip khatian* and Mutation *khatian*. These successive *khatians* along with the title deeds and *bia* deeds are used in establishing the chain of ownership. In case an individual

¹²⁶ The Muslim Personal Law (*Shariat*) Application Act, 1937 (Act No. XXVI of 1937) S. 2.

¹²⁷ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908) S. 17(1) (aa). The clause (aa) was inserted after clause (a) of sub-section 1 of section 17 by Act No. XXV of 2004 with effect from 1st July 2005.

¹²⁸ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908) S. 18. [Any document not required to be registered under section 17 may also be registered under this Act].

¹²⁹ *Ibid*, S. 40.

¹³⁰ *Ibid*, S. 41.

¹³¹ *Ibid*.

¹³² *Ibid*, S. 17(1) (f). The clause (f) was inserted after clause (e) of sub-section 1 of section 17 by Act No. XXV of 2004 (with effect from 1st July 2005).

¹³³ *Ibid*, S. 52A. Section 52A was inserted by section 7 of the Registration (Amendment) Act, 2004 (Act No. XXV of 2004).

¹³⁴ Arif Jamil, Verification of Documents of Land, *the Dhaka University Studies Part-F*, Vol. 17, No. 1, 2006, P. 188.

acquired the land by virtue of inheritance, there would be no title deed in his name. In this situation, *khatians* along with succession certificates and partition deeds may be used to prove the title.

5.4. Rent receipt/ *Dakhila*

After payment of land development taxes, the revenue officer issues a receipt which is called rent receipt or *dakhila*.¹³⁵ A land owner or malik on making payment of his rent is entitled to have a receipt.¹³⁶ It is one of the important instruments to prove title over a land. In the case *Erfan Ali vs. Joynal Abedin Mia*,¹³⁷ the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court held that rent receipts, though not documents of title are important items of evidence of possession and may be used as collateral evidence of title since possession generally follows title.

6. CHALLENGES

The genuineness of the aforementioned instruments is usually established through a rigorous process of verification that is very complex and complicated. For this purpose, the concerned land offices including offices of the Sub-Registrar, Registrar, Assistant Commissioner (Land) and *Tehshilder* as well as District Record Room attached to the office of Deputy Commissioner are required to be visited with a view to inspect and relevant books and volumes.

Record of rights can be verified and a certified copy thereof can be collected from the concerned district record room. A mutation can be verified by inspecting Register IX in the office of the Assistant Commissioner (Land). Reference of the mutation case number is found on the first page of the mutation *khatian*. A registered title deed can be verified or inspected and certified copy thereof can be taken on depositing prescribed fees from the office in which the deed was registered.¹³⁸ Reference of the deed is specified on the back of the last page of the deed. The book number, volume number, page number, deed number and the date or year of registration is good reference of searching a deed in the office of the Registrar.

However, due to manual and obsolete process of land survey and record management,¹³⁹ land records and documents may get damaged at various stages. For instance, a land owner has to file an application with prescribed fees to the office of the Deputy Commissioner in order to have the duplicate copies of record of rights. Sometimes, the district record room cannot provide the applicant with duplicate copies as a result of damage of the main volume.

Complicated system of land management is another hindrance to verify the authenticity of various instruments of land. The land management is entrusted with three basic functions namely, (a) survey of land and settlement, (b) record keeping and (c) registration of land transfer. These functions are carried out by several ministries and government departments. Lack of coordination among these departments generates problems as to multiplicity of land documents and records. As such, one party may bring a proof of ownership from *Tahsil* office, another from Registrar's office

¹³⁵ The State Acquisition and Tenancy Act, 1950 (Act No. of 1951) S. 2(22).

¹³⁶ *Ibid*, S. 138.

¹³⁷ 35 DLR (AD) 216.

¹³⁸ Arif Jamil, Verification of Documents of Land, *the Dhaka University Studies Part - F*, Vol. 17, No. 1, 2006, P. 188.

¹³⁹ According to section 51 of the Registration Act, 1908, the registered documents of transfer of movable and immovable properties are preserved in hand-written register books.

and yet another from the settlement office. If there happens to be a difference, which is obvious, how the court is to adjudicate the dispute?¹⁴⁰

Taking advantages of unsound land transfer process, the unscrupulous people prepare the forged title deeds. Some transfers occur on an entirely unofficial basis, perhaps when land is mortgaged. The registering officer is required to ensure before registration of an instrument that following particulars are included in and attached with the instrument:¹⁴¹

- i. the latest *khatian* of the property in the name of the seller;
- ii. nature of the property;
- iii. price of the property;
- iv. a map of the property together with the axes and boundaries;
- v. a brief description of the ownership of the property for the last 25 years; and
- vi. an affidavit by the executant affirming that he has not transferred the property to any person before execution of this instrument and that he has lawful title thereto.

However, there is no requirement to check the legality of the transaction and it is not uncommon for the same piece of land to be sold to several different buyers, although this is much more frequent in urban areas.¹⁴² Before registering the deed of sale, the Sub-registrar has to establish that the sale money has been paid and to collect the immovable property transfer tax. But the reality is different in most of the cases because of the intrigue of the deed writers, Sub-Registrar as well as the seller. Moreover, procrastination in judicial land disputes settlement, corruption in land services and shortcoming in the existing laws and policies dealing with land related issues pose challenges in governance of land administration.¹⁴³

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The settlement of land disputes in Bangladesh is very complicated. As the foregoing discussion reveals, the existing framework for settlement of land disputes is beset with a number of problems and challenges. The laws and policies dealing with settlement of land disputes are age-old and mostly inherited from the colonial regime which in many instances are found to be ineffective to address the issues and challenges the present land administration is facing. The issues that need urgent attention include determination of land ownership, ensuring coordination among various government agencies dealing with land related services, land survey and record, checking damage of land record at various levels, registration of land transfer, wide spread corruption and so forth.

Establishment of Digital Land Management System (DLMS) is the *sine qua non* to secure automation of land management. Within this system land records are to get computerized and as such the land owners would have easy access to land records that would reduce the chances of fraud and forgery with respect to land ownership. Consequently, land disputes would be lessened significantly relieving the judiciary of the burden of mounting case backlogs. Moreover, a ‘Land Bank’ should be established to ensure digitalized service delivery of the land offices to the citizen.

¹⁴⁰ Mohammad Iqbal Hasan, Land administration in Bangladesh: Problems and analytical approach to solution, *International Journal of Law*, Vol. 3, No. 2, 2017, P. 46.

¹⁴¹ The Registration Act, 1908 (Act No. XVI of 1908), S. 52A. This section was inserted by section 7 of the Registration (Amendment) Act, 2004 (Act No. XXV of 2004).

¹⁴² CARE, *Land Policy and Administration in Bangladesh: A Literature Review*, Care Livelihood Programs, 2003, available at http://carebangladesh.org/publication/Publication_7013284.pdf, retrieved on November 6, 2019.

¹⁴³ Alam, Md. Waheed, *et al. Land Management and Services in Bangladesh: Governance Challenges and Way-forward*, Transparency International Bangladesh, August 2015.

This will bring down the number of land related disputes and establish fair justice in the land related complication. Though the government has undertaken some pilot projects to introduce Automation of Land Management, the objectives of such projects have yet to be achieved. Therefore, the century old legal and institutional frameworks need to have a paradigm shift with a view to easing the intricate and cumbersome land dispute settlement procedure in Bangladesh.